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Lict k-Domination in Graphs

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Abstract

Objectives: In this study, we find lict k -domination number ($\gamma_{kn}(G)$) of various types of graphs. **Methods:** Let G be any graph, a set $D \subseteq V[n(G)]$ is said to be an k -dominating set of lict graph $n(G)$ if every vertex $v \in V[n(G)] - D$ is dominated by at least k vertices in D , that is $|N(v) \cap D| \geq k$. The Lict k -domination number $\gamma_{kn}(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of k -dominating set of $n(G)$. **Findings:** This study is centered on the lict k -domination number $\gamma_{kn}(G)$ of the graph G and developed its relationship with other different domination parameters. **Novelty:** This study introduces the concept of "Lict k -Domination in Graphs". It obtains many bounds on $\gamma_{kn}(G)$ in terms of vertices, edges, and other different parameters of G .

Keywords: Domination number; k -domination number; Lict graph; Lict k -domination number; Total domination number; Independent domination number

1 Introduction

This study considers simple, finite, non-trivial, undirected and connected graph denoted as $G(V, E) = (p, q)$, where V represents the vertex set and E denotes the edge set of the graph. The order and size of graph G is the $|V(G)| = p$ and $|E(G)| = q$. For our notation and corresponding definitions, we follow the F. Harary⁽¹⁾. A lict graph⁽²⁾ $n(G)$ associated with graph G is constructed with a vertex set that is the union of the sets of edges and cut vertices of graph G . In this context, two vertices in $n(G)$ are adjacent if and only if their corresponding edges in graph G are adjacent, or the corresponding elements of G are incident (Figure 1).

We begin by recalling some definitions from domination theory.

A set $D \subseteq V(G)$ is a dominating set if for each vertex $u \in D \subseteq V(G)$, $N(D) \cap D \neq \emptyset$. The domination number $\gamma(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of a dominating set of G . If every vertex in $V(G)$ is connected to at least one neighbor in D , then the subset $D \subseteq V(G)$ is defined as a total dominating set. The total domination number $\gamma_t(G)$ is represents the cardinality of a minimum total dominating set⁽³⁾. A subset $D \subseteq V(G)$ is an independent dominating set if the induced subgraph $\langle D \rangle$ contains no edges. The independence domination number $\gamma_i(G)$ is corresponds to the cardinality of a minimum independence dominating set (see⁽⁴⁾).

2 Related work

Many authors studied different domination in lict graph of graph. In⁽⁵⁾ author introduce the new concept weak domination in lict graphs and determine upper and lower bounds for $\gamma_{wn}(G)$ in terms of parameter graph G . In the context of⁽⁶⁾ the focus is on set domination in lict graphs and develop the properties of the set-domination. Also, relate $\gamma_s(G)$ with some domination parameter. In⁽⁷⁾ studied Split Domination in Lict Subdivision Graph of a Graph and many bounds were obtained in terms of the various element of G . Additionally, they investigated relation between other different domination parameters of graph. Also, in Lict Subdivision Connected Domination in Graphs⁽⁸⁾ work on $\gamma_{nsc}(G)$ to relate this with the components of G .

The Concept of k -domination and its generalization as total k -domination number $\gamma_{kt}(G)$ used in⁽⁹⁾ strong product graph to obtain several bounds for the $\gamma_{kt}(G)$ of the strong product of two graphs. As in 2020, Ekinci G.B., Bujtas C. characterized bipartite graphs satisfying the equality for $k \geq 3$ and presented a necessary and sufficient condition for a bipartite graph to satisfy the equality hereditarily if $k = 3$ ⁽¹⁰⁾. In 2022⁽¹¹⁾, author studied relationships between the k -tuple domination number and parameters of graph and different dominations. Also,⁽¹²⁾ studied the total k -domination number of Cartesian product of two complete graphs and obtained some lower and upper bounds for the total k -domination number of Cartesian product of two complete graphs.

This work uses the concept of k -domination within the lict graph of graph G . The lict k -domination number denoted as $\gamma_{kn}(G)$, represents the minimum cardinality among all k -dominating set of lict graph $n(G)$. Our investigation yields numerous bounds on $\gamma_{kn}(G)$ in terms various parameters such as vertices, edges, and other distinct parameters of G . Additionally, this study establishes relationships between $\gamma_{kn}(G)$ other different domination parameters of G .

3 Methodology

Theorem 2.1.^(13,14) A subset $D \subseteq V(G)$ is k -dominating set if every vertex of $D \subseteq V(G)$ is adjacent to at least k vertices of D . The k -domination number $\gamma_k(G)$ represents the minimum cardinality of k -dominating set of G .

Theorem 2.2.⁽¹⁵⁾ For any Tree T , $\gamma_{se}(n(T)) \leq c$, where c is the number of cut-vertices of T .

Theorem 2.3.⁽¹⁶⁾ For any connected graph G , $\gamma_c(G) \geq \gamma(G)$.

Theorem 2.4.⁽¹⁶⁾ For any connected graph G with $p \geq 2$ vertices, $\gamma_{ct}(G) \geq \gamma_t(G)$.

Theorem 2.5.⁽¹⁵⁾ For any connected graph G , $\gamma_{se}(n(G)) \geq \gamma'(G)$.

Theorem 2.6.⁽¹⁷⁾ For any graph G , $\gamma_t(n(G)) \geq \gamma'(G)$.

4 Results and Discussion

Theorem 3.1: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \frac{q+c}{\Delta'(n(G))+1}$.

Proof. Let $V(n(G))$ be the set $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{q+c}\}$, representing the vertex set of the lict graph of graph G . There exists a minimal set $A_1 = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{q+c}\} \subseteq V(n(G))$, such that every vertex in $V(n(G)) - A_1$ is adjacent to at least k vertices of A_1 . This establishes A_1 as the minimal k -dominating set of $n(G)$. Clearly, $|A_1| = \gamma_{kn}(G)$.

It gives that each vertex in $V(n(G)) - A_1$ contributes at least one to the sum of degree of vertices of A_1 . This implies that the size of set $(V(n(G)) - A_1)$ is less than or equal to the sum of the degrees of vertices in A_1 , given by:

$$|V(n(G)) - A_1| \leq \sum_{u_i \in A_1} deg(u_i)$$

In the lict graph $n(G)$, there exists at least one vertex $u_j \in V(n(G))$ such that $deg(u_i) = \Delta'(n(G))$.

We can conclude that,

$$q + c - \gamma_{kn}(G) = |V(n(G)) - A_1| \leq \sum_{u_i \in A_1} deg(u_i) \leq \gamma_{kn}(G) * \Delta'(n(G)).$$

Therefore, $q + c - \gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \gamma_{kn}(G) * \Delta'(n(G))$.

Thus, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \frac{q+c}{\Delta'(n(G))+1}$.

Theorem 3.2: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph with $2 \leq k \leq \Delta(G)$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \gamma(G) + k - 2$.

Proof. Let $V(G) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p\}$ represent the vertex set a graph G . Then, there is subset D of $V(G)$ that covers all the vertices of G . This shows that D is dominating set of G . Consider $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ as the vertex set of lict graph of graph G , and let $S \subseteq V(n(G))$ be a minimum k -dominating set of $n(G)$.

Now, take $w \in V(n(G)) - S$, and let w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k be distinct vertices in S which dominate w . Since S is a k -dominating set, each vertex in $V(n(G)) - S$ is dominated by at least one vertex in $S - \{w_2, w_3, \dots, w_k\}$. Therefore, w dominates each vertex in $\{w_2, w_3, \dots, w_k\}$.

Which implies,

$$|D| \leq |S - \{w_2, w_3, \dots, w_k\} \cup \{w\}|$$

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma(G) &\leq \gamma_{kn}(G) - (k - 1) + 1 \\ &= \gamma_{kn}(G) - k + 2 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \gamma(G) + k - 2$.

Theorem 3.3: For any graph $G = (p, q)$ and a positive integer $k \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq c$. Where c is number of cut vertices of G .

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, then result holds trivially.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

Assume $A_1 = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_c\}$ be subset of a vertex set of $n(G)$ contains cut vertices of G . Let $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q, m_1, m_2, \dots, m_c\}$ be a vertex set of $n(G)$, where w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q corresponds to edges incident on vertices of graph G .

Consider a subset D_1 of $V(n(G))$, which contains vertices of $n(G)$ which corresponding to edges incident with cut vertices of graph G . Then, D_1 forms a minimal k -dominating set of lict graph of G . Otherwise, we can add cut vertices in D_1 to get a k -dominating set of $V(n(G))$. A cardinality of such a set is greater or equal to the number of cut vertices of G .

Therefore, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq c$.

Corollary 3.4: For any tree T and a positive integer $k \geq 2$ then $\gamma_{kn}(T) \geq \gamma_{se}(n(T))$.

Proof. From Theorem 2.2, we have

$$\gamma_{se}(n(T)) \leq c \tag{1}$$

From Theorem 3.3, we get

$$\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq c \tag{2}$$

From Equations (1) and (2), we Conclude that, this is required result.

Theorem 3.5: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph and k is a positive integer with $k \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \gamma_i(G)$.

Proof. Let $A = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\}$ be a dominating set of G . If the induces subgraph $\langle A \rangle$ contains vertices of degree zero, then A itself is an independent dominating set. Otherwise, let $S = A_1 \cup A_2$, where $A_1 \subseteq A$ and $A_2 \subseteq V(G) - A$ forming a minimal independent dominating set of G such that $|S| = \gamma_i(G)$.

Now, consider $D = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_s, m_1, m_2, \dots, m_t\}$, a subset of vertex set of $V(n(G))$, where e_i 's are edges incident on vertices of set S and m_i 's are the cut vertices of G . If every vertex of $V(n(G)) - D$ is adjacent to at least k vertices of D then D itself is

a k -dominating set of $n(G)$. Otherwise, let $S_1 = D_1 \cup D_2$, where $D_1 \subseteq D$ and $D_2 \subseteq V(n(G)) - D$, forms minimal k -dominating set of $n(G)$, and it gives $|S| \leq |S_1|$.

Thus, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \gamma(G)$.

Theorem 3.6: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph and k is a positive integer with $k \leq \Delta(G)$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma(n(G)) \geq q + c$.

Proof. For $k \leq \Delta(G)$, let $S = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_r\} \subseteq V(n(G))$ be minimal k -dominating set of $n(G)$. Assume that there exists vertex $w \in S$ that is not adjacent to any vertex in $V(n(G)) - S$. This implies that w is adjacent to at least k vertices of set S . This Shows that the set $S - \{w\}$ is minimal k -dominating set of $n(G)$. Which contradicts the set S is minimal k -dominating set. Therefore, every vertex in S is adjacent to at least one vertex of $V(n(G)) - S$. This implies $V(n(G)) - S$ is dominating set of $n(G)$. Clearly, there exists set $D \subseteq [V(n(G)) - S]$ is minimal dominating set of $n(G)$ such that $|D| + |S| \leq q + c$.

Thus, $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma(n(G)) \geq q + c$.

Theorem 3.7: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph. Then, $\gamma'(G) \leq \gamma(n(G)) \leq \gamma_{kn}(G)$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, the result holds obviously.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

Let $E(G) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_q\}$ be edge set of G , and $C(G) = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_c\}$ be set of cut vertices of G . The vertex set of lict graph is $V(n(G)) = E(G) \cup C(G)$. Let $E_1 = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_s\} \subseteq E(G)$ be minimal edge dominating set of G such that $|E_1| = \gamma'(G)$. Since $E(G) \subseteq V(n(G))$, if set E_1 forms a dominating set of $n(G)$ then result holds. Otherwise, let $A = V(n(G)) - E_1$, then $A_1 \cup E_2$, where $A_1 \subseteq A$ and $E_2 \subseteq E_1$ covers all vertices of $n(G)$, and which is minimal dominating set of $n(G)$.

Clearly, $|E_1| \leq |A_1 \cup E_2|$.

Therefore, $\gamma'(G) \leq \gamma(n(G))$. Also, we get required result.

Theorem 3.8: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph. Then, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq q + \alpha_0(G)$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, the result holds obviously.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

As $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ contains q edges and c cut vertices. Let $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ Subset $V(n(G))$ corresponding to edges of graph G . A set $A = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\}$ be the vertex cover of G , which also contain a cut vertices of graph G . Consider $E_1 \subseteq E$ and $A_1 \subseteq A$, then $A_1 \cup E_1$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$ such that $|A_1 \cup E_1| \leq |E| + |A|$.

We get, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq q + \alpha_0(G)$.

Theorem 3.9: Let $G = (p, q)$ be any graph. Then, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq p + \alpha_1(G)$.

Proof. Let $A = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p\}$ be vertex set of graph G . A set $B = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_s\}$ is edge cover of graph G such that $|B| = \alpha_1(G)$.

As $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ is the vertex set of $n(G)$, which is a collection of edges and cut vertices of G . We take a set $D_1 = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q\}$ be the edges incident on vertices of G , and $C_1 = \{w_{q+1}, w_{q+2}, \dots, w_{q+i}\}$ are the cut vertices adjacent to element of edge cover of G . Consider $D_2 \subseteq D_1$ and $C_2 \subseteq C_1$, then $D_2 \cup C_2$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$.

Clearly, $|D_2 \cup C_2| \leq |A| + |B|$.

Thus, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq p + \alpha_1(G)$.

Theorem 3.10: Let $G = (p, q)$ be any graph. Then, $\gamma_{kn}(G) < q + \text{diam}(G)$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, the vertex set of lict graph contains vertices, which corresponds to edges of G , such that $|V(n(G))| = q$. This follows the result.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

As vertex set of $n(G)$ is $V(n(G)) = E(G) \cup C(G)$, where $E(G)$ is the edge set of G and $C(G)$ is set of cut vertices of G . Let $E = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q\}$ subset $V(n(G))$ corresponding to the edges of graph G . A set $D = \{w_{q+1}, w_{q+2}, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ be cut vertices of G , which are lie on the longest path between two vertices u_1 and u_2 of G such that $\text{dist}(u_1, u_2) = \text{diam}(G)$. Consider $E_1 \subseteq E$ and $D_1 \subseteq D$, then $E_1 \cup D_1$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$.

It follows that, $|E_1 \cup D_1| < |E| + \text{dist}(u_1, u_2)$.

We get, $\gamma_{kn}(G) < q + \text{diam}(G)$.

Theorem 3.11: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph. Then, $\gamma_{kn}(G) < q + \beta_0(G)$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, the result holds.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

A vertex set of $n(G)$ is a collection those vertices which corresponds to edges and cut vertices of G . Let $E = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q\}$ subset $V(n(G))$ corresponding to edges of graph G , and set $B = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\}$ be the maximum independent set of G such that $|B| = \beta_0(G)$. Consider set $C = \{w_{q+1}, w_{q+2}, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ contain cut vertices of G which are either member of B or adjacent to elements of B such that $|C| < |B|$.

Let $E_1 \subseteq E$ and $C_1 \subseteq C$, then $E_1 \cup C_1$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$.

Clearly, $|E_1 \cup C_1| < |E| + |B|$.

Thus, $\gamma_{kn}(G) < q + \beta_0(G)$.

Theorem 3.12: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph. Then, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq q + \gamma_i(G)$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, then result holds.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

Let $D = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\}$ be a dominating set of G and $D_1 = V(G) - D$ be a set such that $H \subseteq D_1$ with a minimum set of vertices. If $\langle D \rangle$ does not contain an isolated vertex, then D itself total dominating set of G . Otherwise, some $u_i \in H$ such that $\forall u_j \in D, (u_i, u_j) \in E(G)$

and $\langle D_1 \rangle = \langle D \cup \{u_i\} \rangle$ has no isolated vertex. Then $D_1 = D \cup \{u_i\}$ is a total dominating set of G such that $D_1 = \gamma_i(G)$.

Let $E = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q\}$ subset $V(n(G))$ corresponding to edges of graph G . A set $D_1 = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_i\}$ be a minimal total dominating set, and the cut vertices are also member of such set. Let $E_1 \subseteq E$ and $D_2 \subseteq D_1$, then $E_1 \cup D_2$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$. It gives, $|E_1 \cup D_2| \leq |E| + |D_1|$.

Hence, the result.

Theorem 3.13: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph and k is a positive integer with $k \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \frac{p}{\Delta'(G)}$

Proof. Let $V(G) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p\}$ be vertex set of G , and $E(G) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_q\}$ are edges incident on vertices of G . Which are members of vertex set of $n(G)$, and set $E(G) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_q\}$ cut vertices of G .

For $k \geq 2, V(n(G)) = E(G) \cup C(G)$ be a vertex set of lict graph of G . Then, there exists a set B such that every vertex of $V(n(G)) - B$ adjacent to at least k vertices of B . This implies that B forms minimal k -dominating set of $n(G)$. for every graph, there exists an edge $e \in E(G)$ of maximum degree, i.e., $deg(e) = \Delta'(G)$ Such that, $\Delta'(G) * |B| \geq |V(G)|$.

$$\therefore \Delta'(G) * \gamma_{kn}(G) \geq p$$

$$\text{Thus, } \gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \frac{p}{\Delta'(G)}$$

Theorem 3.14: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma_i(G) \leq q + p$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq q$ and $\gamma_i(G) \leq p$. We get required result.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

Let $V(G) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p\}$ be vertex set of G then there exists a set $A = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\} \subseteq V(G)$ such that $\langle A \rangle$ has a no isolated vertex. This shows A is total dominating set of G and $|A| = \gamma_i(G)$.

Let set $C = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_c\}$ be the cut vertices of G and $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_q\}$ be edge set of G . Which are the members of vertex set of $n(G)$. Consider $E_1 \subseteq E$ and $C_1 \subseteq C$, then $E_1 \cup C_1$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$ such that $|E_1 \cup C_1| + |A| \leq |E(G)| + |V(G)|$.

$$\text{Thus, } \gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma_i(G) \leq q + p$$

Theorem 3.15: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma(G) \geq \gamma_i(G)$.

Proof. Case-I: If $\gamma(G) = \gamma_i(G)$, then the result holds clearly.

Case-II: If $\gamma(G) \neq \gamma_i(G)$.

Let $D = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p\}$ be a dominating set of G and $\langle D \rangle$ contain isolated vertex. Then, there exists $u_i \in V(G) - D$ such that $\forall u_j \in D, (u_i, u_j) \in E(G)$ and $\langle D_1 \rangle = \langle D \cup \{u_i\} \rangle$ has no isolated vertex. Then, $D_1 = D \cup \{u_i\}$ is total dominating set of G . Which contains cut vertices of G and $V(n(G))$ be vertex set of $n(G)$ contains vertices which correspond to edges and cut vertices of G . So, there is minimal set $A \subseteq V(n(G))$ which is k -dominating set of $n(G)$ such that, $|A| + |D| \geq |D_1|$.

$$\text{We get, } \gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma(G) \geq \gamma_i(G)$$

Corollary 3.16: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma_c(G) \geq \gamma_i(G)$.

Proof. Using Theorem 2.2 and Theorem 3.16, we get required result.

Theorem 3.17: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma_i(G) \leq q + p$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq q$ and $\gamma_i(G) \leq p$. We get required result.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

Let $A = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\}$ be dominating set of G . If induced subgraph $\langle A \rangle$ contains vertices of degree zero, then set A itself minimal independent dominating set of G . Otherwise, $S = A_1 \cup A_2$, where $A_1 \subseteq A$ and $A_2 \subseteq V(G) - A$ forms minimal independent dominating set of G such that $|S| = \gamma_i(G)$.

A set $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_q\}$ be edge set of G and $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_q\}$ be set of cut vertices of G . The vertex set of lict graph is $V(n(G)) = E(G) \cup C(G)$. Consider $E_1 \cup C_1$, where $E_1 \subseteq E$ and $C_1 \subseteq C$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$ such that $|E_1 \cup C_1| + |S| \leq |V(G)| + |E(G)|$.

$$\text{Thus, } \gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma_i(G) \leq q + p$$

Theorem 3.18: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq diam(G) + \beta_0(G) + \Delta'(G)$.

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex.

In this scenario, $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q\}$ is the vertex set of $n(G)$ with vertices corresponding to edges incident on vertices of G . Let $D = \{e_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq s\}$ be the edges lying on the longest path between two vertices u and v of G . Additionally, let $A = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_i\}$ be maximum independent set of G and $B = \{e_j \mid 1 \leq j \leq m\}$ be edges such that e_j incident on u_j , for all $u_j \in A$. Set $C = \{e_r \mid 1 \leq r \leq l\}$ consist of edges adjacent to an edge of maximum degree other than the element of D and B such that $|C| \leq \Delta'(G)$. Consider $D_1 \cup B_1 \cup C_1$, where $D_1 \subseteq D$, $C_1 \subseteq C$ and $B_1 \subseteq B$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$, such that $|D_1 \cup B_1 \cup C_1| \leq |D| + |B| + |C|$.

This implies that, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \text{diam}(G) + \beta_0(G) + \Delta'(G)$.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices.

In this case, $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ be vertex set of $n(G)$ with vertices of lict graph corresponding to edges and cut vertices of G . Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_s\}$ contain vertices of lict graph corresponding to all cut vertices lying on the longest path between two vertices u and v of G such that $|U| = \text{diam}(G)$. Additionally, let $T = \{e_r \mid 1 \leq r \leq l\}$ be edges adjacent to an edge of maximum degree such that $|T| = \Delta'(G)$, and let $S = \{e_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq t\}$ contains edges such that e_i incident on u_i , for all $u_i \in A$, where $A = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ is maximum independent set. Consider $U_1 \cup T_1 \cup S_1$, where $U_1 \subseteq U$, $T_1 \subseteq T$ and $S_1 \subseteq S$ forms minimal a k -dominating set of $n(G)$, such that $|U_1 \cup T_1 \cup S_1| \leq |U| + |T| + |S|$.

This implies that, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \text{diam}(G) + \beta_0(G) + \Delta'(G)$.

Thus, it follows the result.

Theorem 3.19: If $G = (p, q)$ is any graph and k is a positive integer with $k \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \beta_1(G)$.

Proof. Let $A = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_s\}$ be maximum subset of the edge set of G . Where no two edges from set A are adjacent. Therefore, $|A| = \beta_1(G)$. A set $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ be vertex set of $n(G)$ with vertices correspond to edges and cut vertices of G .

For $k \geq 2$, if every vertex of $V(n(G)) - A$ is adjacent to at least k vertices of A , then A is minimal k -dominating set of $n(G)$. Otherwise, by adding vertices from $V(n(G)) - A$ to set A , we can obtain a minimal k -dominating set of $n(G)$.

Clearly, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \beta_1(G)$.

This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.20: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \alpha_1(G) + \alpha_0(G) + \gamma_l(G)$.

Proof. Let $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ be vertex set of $n(G)$ and members of $V(n(G))$ correspond to edges and cut vertices of G . Let $A_1 = \{e_i \mid 1 \leq i \leq s\}$ be minimal edge cover set of G such that $|A_1| = \alpha_1(G)$. Also, let $A_2 = \{e_j \mid 1 \leq j \leq t\}$ contains edges of G incident on vertices of minimal vertex cover set of G such that $|A_2| = \alpha_0(G)$. Additionally, let $T = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ be a minimal total dominating set of G , where cut vertices of G are members of T .

Consider, $A \subseteq A_1$, $A_3 \subseteq A_2$ and $T_1 \subseteq T$, then $A \cup A_3 \cup T_1$ forms minimal a T k -dominating set of $n(G)$ such that: $|A \cup A_3 \cup T_1| \leq |A_1| + |A_2| + |T|$.

Therefore, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \alpha_1(G) + \alpha_0(G) + \gamma_l(G)$.

Theorem 3.21: For any graph $G = (p, q)$ and a positive integer k . If $k = \Delta(n(G))$ then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq q + c - s$, where s is number of vertices of degree $\Delta(n(G))$.

Proof. The lict graph has $q + c$ vertices, consisting q edges and c cut vertices. Let $S = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_s\}$ contains a vertices of degree $\Delta(n(G))$. The proof is divided into two cases.

Case-I: $|S| = 1$.

In this case, the result hold trivially.

Case-II: $|S| > 1$,

Subcase-I. For $k = \Delta(n(G))$, if the members of S are adjacent to each other:

In this scenario, a k -dominating set contain $|S| - 1$ vertices from S . We get required result.

Subcase-II. For $k = \Delta(n(G))$, if the members of S are not adjacent to each other:

In this case, there exists k members from $V(n(G))$ other than member of S adjacent to every vertex of S . we get, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq q + c - s$.

Therefore, the theorem holds true.

Theorem 3.22: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \gamma_{kl}(G) + c$, where c is number of cut vertices of G .

Proof. Case-I: If the graph has no cut vertex:

In this case, the result holds because the lict graph coincides with line graph.

Case-II: If the graph has cut vertices:

Let D be k dominating set of $L(G)$ and S be set of cut vertices of G , which are not incident with any edge of D . For every cut vertex $u \in S$, consider exactly one edge in E_1 , where $E_1 = \{e_j \in E(G) \mid e_j \text{ incident with } u \text{ and } e_j \in N(D)\}$ such that, $|E_1| \leq |S|$. This implies that $D \cup E_1$ forms minimal k -dominating set of lict graph of G . It follows that $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \gamma_{kl}(G) + |S|$.

Therefore, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq \gamma_{kl}(G) + c$.

Theorem 3.23: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph and a positive integer k with $k \leq \delta(G)$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq p$

Proof. Let $V(G) = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_p\}$ be vertex set of G and $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ be the vertex set of lict graph of G . We consider subset $D_1 = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ of $V(n(G))$, which corresponds to edges incident on vertices of G and cut vertices of G .

For $k \leq \delta(G)$, there exists $D_2 \subseteq D_1$ is minimal k -dominating set of lict graph of G such that $|D_2| \leq |V(G)| = p$.

Therefore, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq p$, and the proof is complete.

Theorem 3.24: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph and a positive integer k with $k \leq \delta(G)$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq q$.

Proof. Let $V(n(G)) = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{q+c}\}$ be the vertex set of lict graph of G . Consider the subset $E = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_q\}$ of $V(n(G))$ with vertices of E corresponding to edges incident on vertices of G such that $|E| = q$.

For $k \leq \delta(G)$, then there exists a possible $E_1 \subseteq E$ that is minimal k -dominating set of lict graph of G such that $|E_1| \leq |E|$.

Therefore, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \leq q$.

Theorem 3.25: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph and a positive integer k with $k \geq \Delta(G)$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \Delta(G)$.

Proof. Since for every k , and $k \geq \Delta(n(G))$, it follows that $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \Delta(n(G))$.

For any graph $\Delta(n(G)) \geq \Delta(G)$.

Therefore, $\gamma_{kn}(G) \geq \Delta(G)$.

Theorem 3.26: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph with $p \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma'(G) \leq q + \gamma_{ct}(G) + \gamma_{se}(n(G))$.

Proof. Using Theorem 2.3, Theorem 2.5 and Theorem 3.12, we get the required result.

Theorem 3.27: If $G = (p, q)$ be any graph with $p \geq 2$, then $\gamma_{kn}(G) + \gamma'(G) \leq q + \gamma_{ct}(G) + \gamma(n(G))$.

Proof. Using Theorem 2.3, Theorem 2.6 and Theorem 3.12, we get the required result.

5 Conclusion

This study has computed the results regarding k -domination in lict graph. The study involves deriving theorems specifically related to lict k -domination and relationships with various other domination parameters. Furthermore, this investigation derivation of lict k -domination number, denoted as $\gamma_{kn}(G)$, considering factors such as vertices, edges, and various other parameters of graph G .

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